

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ECONOMIC EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. The article covers the theoretical foundations of the use of innovative technologies in the provision of economic upbringing to preschool children, the advantages of introducing innovative technologies into preschool education and the analysis of innovative methods in the provision of economic upbringing to children.

Keywords: globalization, innovation, innovative activity, agglutination, mental cell, continuing education, economic education, technology.

Globalization requires rapid movement on its own, the immediate capture of the necessary information, their processing and effective implementation in practice. The fact that in the content of educational reforms, the issuance of scientific knowledge to the younger generation, the formation of a broad worldview in them and the establishment of new requirements for the upbringing of spiritual and moral qualities indicate the need to find a decision on an innovative approach to the organization of pedagogical activity. One of the conditions for achieving high efficiency in the organization of educational and spiritual and educational work at all stages of the system of continuing education is the introduction of innovative technologies into the activities of educational institutions and its introduction into the educational process, and not only the educational process.

All this is due to the fact that the president of our Republic Sh.Mirziyoyev testifies to the fact that in the next five years, having approved a number of documents on the reform of the field of preschool education and education, he introduced it into practice. The issue of bringing innovative technologies in the field of preschool education and education and its implementation in the activities of preschool educational organizations is still relevant today counted. We below is the concept of innovation, its content, methodological foundations, we reflect on the importance in the educational process and the possibility of using innovative technologies in economic education for Children of preschool age. The lexical meaning of the concept of "innovation" is "innovating", logically

recognized as" changing the internal structure of the system." Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, a system of action of social entities aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object. The reflection of new social relations in educational programs of an innovative nature is characterized by the emergence of interaction between educators, students and their parents.

To practice educational programs with an innovative character. In the implementation, the educational system of the pedagogical community and parents provides for the same active participation of governing bodies, state and local organizations, as well as institutions operating in social and commercial directions. In recent years, views have been formed among the pedagogical community that express the purposefulness of the implementation of the task of organizing the activities of educational institutions by social institutions. This means that the educational system is managed on the basis of mutual cooperation between public bodies and social organizations. This cooperation allows social organizations to control the activities of educational institutions together with state bodies. Such an opportunity means the possibility of supporting educational projects, the distribution of the budget allocated for educational institutions, the determination of their strategy and the emergence of social influences on the process of preschool education.

In this respect, any scientific and technical activity can be recognized as innovation. In particular, "innovative activities cannot be compared to activities in the field of scientific creativity, since such an analogy shallower the meaning of the term" innovative activities". Because any scientific and technical activity is innovative in its nature. Therefore, it is necessary to consider innovative activities in a certain area of social practice. This practice can be considered innovative, from the point of view of a specific subject and any activity that leads to serious changes in the current tradition. Expressing the concept of innovation in Uzbek in such a sense as new, novelty is also considered correct. S.I.Ojegov defines the concept of new as follows: first formed .Either created, appeared or arose recently, arose instead of the previous one, referred to the recent past, or has not been sufficiently or so known to the present". As it turned out, the explanation for the concept was not addressed in terms of progressiveness, the effectiveness of the novelty. It can be said that not all innovations will have an advanced feature. On the basis of progress, efficiency, efficiency are expressed in the first place.

Economic education of preschool children has been and remains one of the main problems of pedagogy. It is important to form children's economic thinking

both in one context and in subsequent development, which is moving towards a market economy. Our government is taking care of this area, and there is a lot of research on the issue of the use of innovative technologies in the economic education of children by specialists in the field. The main goal of providing economic education to preschool children forms the ability of children to make savings, business, economic calculations. The content of Economic Education was regularly enriched and scientifically substantiated by Eastern thinkers. In this regard, Al-Khwarazmi particularly emphasizes that mathematics plays a central role in human life. In his opinion, a person should know the science of accounting and be thorough in his work. Then he says that he can determine the results of his labor (as well as others) through measurements. A. Avlonius further advanced such valuable ideas as "economy, knowledge of the value of favors such as money and goods", and "knowledge and goods are necessary to reach the goal in the present time, to be acceptable to the people". For example, let's see his comments: "The Americans plant a piece of wheat and take twenty packs of wheat, and the Europeans sell us our 5 kopecks of cotton for 25 kopecks. But we, Asians, in particular, turkestanis, buy buttocks and chew chanter: we bite off sour cream, instead of bread, in short, in order to become a person in accordance with the present, you need an economy equal to science and Education, an economy that does not end in moderation, an inexhaustible zeal."

To discover is the ability of children to discover through the method, the power of fantasy is increased. Children are left with an initial trigger question, "if...". Children will have to continue the process, relying on their imagination. For example, "if I remain water...", "if the sun does not rise on Earth every day...", "if there is no water...". Image images-in this method, the object is studied emotionally-figuratively. As a result of analyzing or observing the selected object, the child is required to create a textual or graphic image of his imagination. The goal of this method is to teach children to independently think about the development of figurative thinking, analytical thinking, their imagination, fantasy and the use of each item in their place.

Agglutination is a method through which children can create different, unrealistic B dead objects or images through their imagination. For example, the ice age, are also the product of agglutination. The mental attack-method encourages children to form skills, competencies about broad and comprehensive thinking about the subject, the positive use of their own imagination, ideas. With it, in organized training, it is possible to find several

original (specific) solutions to voluntary problems. The method creates conditions for the identification of certain views within the framework of the topic, the choice of alternative ideas for them. In training, it is not allowed to control children's activities on the basis of standard requirements, to assess the opinions expressed by them (after all, when opinions are evaluated, children focus their attention on protecting their personal thoughts, as a result of which new thoughts are not put forward. Keeping in mind that the main goal of using the method is to encourage children to think widely about the problem, it is important to refrain from them. "Symbolic view" -in this method, the object is researched by children from an emotional-symbolic point of view. Links between the selected object and its symbol are sought, it is required to create a symbol of the object in any form through graphic, marked, words, the main thing is to interpret, justify this symbol. The purpose of the method is to memorize the acquired knowledge, to be able to generalize the collected information, to teach them to express them in the form of pictures, drawings, to develop their analytical and logical thinking, to form creativity, innovative imagination.

Everistic questions are those that require the method to construct questions based on 7 base interrogative words for the purpose of collecting information about the chosen event or object. Who? What? Where? When? How? In what way? Why? In the process of drawing up beginner questions with questions and finding answers to them, a new "when and in what way?" "Who and when?", "Who and why?" questions arise. In this, the most original, unique questions and clear answers are highly praised. The goal is to penetrate deeply into the content and essence of the studied object, improve the skills of analytical and logical thinking of children and prepare children for innovative activities from the preschool age.

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